

The Development of Thermoelectric-Solar Hybrid Energy Harvester System

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ABSTRACT

Demand growth of power electric increases rapidly today and it is needed to activate the various of electronic equipment. Electric energy today very easily to explore with discovered various of method in generate of electricity through using water energy, wind energy, nuclear energy and solar energy. There were also have power plant likes turbine power plant and diesel power plant using of fossil. Studied of solar cell has been explored since 1839, but electricity that supplied might be very expensive and shortage in source due to dependence of electricity are very high in daily activity. Thus, to generate electricity we must use the source that easily to get and based on renewable energy resources. Solar energy is the one of the renewable energy (RE). RE stands for energy sources that can be replaced within a short period of time after it has been used. Photovoltaic (PV) and thermoelectric generator (TEG) are the devices that can convert solar energy to electric energy. Both PV and TEG devices has been selected to form hybrid power systems based on usage of RE sources. This system is called as thermoelectric-solar hybrid energy. The boost DC-DC converter with Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) technique will be used to produce the maximum output voltage from the hybrid system. The functions and working principle has been discussed in this paper.

Keywords: Photovoltaic; Thermolectric Generator; Maximum Power Point Tracking;

ABSTRAK

Perkembangan permintaan tenaga kuasa elektrik pada hari ini telah meningkat dengan cepat di mana sangat diperlukan untuk menghidupkan pelbagai peralatan elektronik. Tenaga elektrik sangat mudah untuk diterokai dengan penemuan pelbagai kaedah dalam menjana tenaga elektrik iaitu melalui tenaga air, tenaga angin, tenaga nuklear dan tenaga solar. Terdapat juga loji kuasa seperti loji kuasa turbin dan loji kuasa diesel yang menggunakan fosil. Kajian terhadap sel solar telah diterokai sejak tahun 1839 lagi, tetapi tenaga elektrik yang dibekalkan mungkin sangat mahal dan akan kekurangan sumber kerana kebergantungan terhadap tenaga elektrik yang tinggi dalam aktiviti harian. Oleh itu, untuk menjana tenaga elektrik kita mesti menggunakan sumber tenaga yang mudah untuk didapati dan berdasarkan sumber-sumber tenaga yang boleh diperbaharui. Sumber tenaga boleh diperbaharui bermaksud sumber tenaga yang boleh diganti dalam tempoh masa yang singkat selepas ia digunakan. Fotovolta (PV) dan penjana termoelektrik (TEG) adalah peranti yang boleh menukarkan tenaga solar kepada tenaga elektrik. Kedua-dua peranti PV dan TEG telah dipilih untuk membentuk sistem kuasa hibrid berdasarkan penggunaan sumber tenaga yang boleh diperbaharui. Sistem ini dipanggil sebagai tenaga hibrid termoelektrik-solar. Penukar langkah naik (DC-DC) dengan teknik penjejak titik kuasa maxima (MPPT) akan digunakan untuk menghasilkan keluaran voltan maxima daripada sistem hibrid. Fungsi dan prinsip kerja telah dibincangkan dalam kajian ini.

Kata Kunci: (Fotovolta; penjana Termoelektrik; Penjejak Titik Kuasa Maksima).

INTRODUCTION

Renewable energy sources (RESs) are becoming the major importance as alternative electricity generation due to concerns on the increasing level of CO₂ in the atmosphere. Among of the emerging RES technologies, the photovoltaic (PV) system is the most popular as it offers many advantages such as noise free, less maintenance, pollution free and low cost. The capacity of PV installation is increased 60% between 2004-2009 and it is reached to 80% growth in 2011 (Shadmand et al. 2015) and the number keeps increasing over the year. However, the efficiency of PV module conversion efficiency is between 12-20%. The efficiency depends on PV system operation and the conditions of the connected loads. Nevertheless, the efficiency can be improved using MPPT based on DC-DC converter to obtain at the maximum power point voltage at the load terminal (Adly et al. 2012). Several MPPT techniques for standalone applications have been used to improve the efficiency of PV system for specific load conditions. Apart from that, PV module can be used to utilize heat energy in producing electricity. In considering that, a PV system which is known as thermoelectric generator (TEG) module applies Seebeck effect to generate electricity (TEG Power 2011). The TEG module is made of p-type and n-type semiconductor materials to form a thermocouple to convert heat energy into electricity. Over the past few years, researchers worked with the available MPPT algorithms considering constant irradiance and temperature. However, the irradiance and temperature will vary over time. A combination of PV system based on MPPT algorithm and TEG system can help to enhance the overall solar generation. A block diagram of hybrid PV-TEG system is shown in Figure 1. The configuration of hybrid PV-TEG system can be found in either separated or integrated module.

Figure 1 Hybrid PV-TEG system block diagram

A PV-TEG cell operates at room temperature with the solar radiation as input and the total electric power generation as output. The performance of the hybrid system depends on environmental conditions (i.e, temperature and irradiance) and the characteristics of used material which can be measured in terms of total generated electric power and overall system efficiency. In Figure 1, the first block represent the photovoltaic (PV) module and the second block represent thermoelectric generator (TEG) module. In this configuration, the heat energy (Q) start to release when solar radiation strike the PV module and flow to the TEG module. The heat energy dissipates through the hot side (T_h) to cold side (T_c) and create temperature different (ΔT). The higher the temperature different is formed, the higher the voltage will be produced.

METHODOLOGY

The Concept of Photovoltaic System

The output voltage of PV module is depending on two factors; temperature and solar radiation. Higher photocurrent will be induced when more solar radiation strike the PV module and causes higher PV voltage. As a result, more power is produced. On the other hand, higher the module temperature reduces the terminal voltage of the PV

module. In other word, the maximum power can be produced from the PV module when it keeps at low temperature. Therefore, this paper focuses on the produce voltage from the PV module.

Figure 2 The equivalent circuit of Photovoltaic cell

The Concept of Thermoelectric Generator System

TEG generates electricity based on the different temperature between two junctions of used semiconductor materials. The higher terminal voltage can be generated when higher temperature difference is formed. The basic element of the TEG module is a thermocouple. This can be realized using two legs of a different doped semiconductor material (i.e., n-type and p-type) and they are connected to each other through a metal plate, normally copper. The TEG module in form of thermocouples are connected in series electrically and in parallel thermally as illustrated in Figure 3. In this figure, L_{cer} represents the length of ceramic element, L is the length of thermoelement and L_c is the length of chopper contact.

Figure 1 A cross section of TEG module

The performance of the TEG module can be improved when more modules are used. This is because of more electrical power can be produced in the square of metre while the efficiency remains the same. In this paper, six TEG modules are used to generate the highest output voltage. Although the generated power of the TEG module is generally based on the heat input, it also depends on the load conditions.

Figure 4 Block diagram hybrid PV-TEG with DC-DC converter

A DC-DC boost converter with MPPT is used in this experiment to regulate the output voltage from the hybrid system and charge the super-capacitor before it can be transferred to the load. A MATLAB software equipped with DAQ card is used to get the reading and produce graph of the voltage against time. The connection of the PV and TEG are in series.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Basic PV and TEG module performance characterization

For the basic PV and TEG module, the result are more focus on the output voltage. Figure 5 below shows the setup of stand alone PV using halogen lamp as a source replacement for sun in power laboratory and figure 6 is the output voltage from the PV panel.

Figure 5 Setup of PV using halogen lamp

Figure 6 the ouput of stand alone PV

From the experiment, when the halogen lamp switched off there still have a certain voltage value in the PV panel about 0.3-0.5 V. After the halogen lamp turned on, the PV immediately generate the maximum output voltage, 2.1 V. Beyond reach the maximum point, the output will slightly change due to temperature increase in the panel PV. For the TEG, the tes same as the PV but have used other equipment to generate heat. Figure below shows the apparatus setup in the laboratory.

Figure 7 test for TEG with MPPT

Figure 8 output voltage of TEG with MPPT

For this experiment, hot plate were used with the adjustable knob for temperature as the heat source. MPPT with boost converter and capacitor super also used to make sure that the output voltage of the TEG can be step up to 5V and stored in kapasitor super as temporary storage before transfer to load when the source disconnected. DAQ-USB is used to measure every single output voltage from the equipment and transfer to PC through software MATLAB. Figure below show the output from 6 TEG after connect to MPPT and super capacitor.

Based on the graph and table above, voltage produce from 6 TEG are very small and need a much time to increase the output voltage. Its can conclude that, output voltage increase with the temperature different. First MPPT not step up the voltage because the input voltage to MPPT not archieve its specification that is must be more than 0.2 V to activate the MPPT board with step up converter. After transfer to super-capasitor to store the charge, the second MPPT regulates the output voltage at 5V to keep the voltage at maximum point.

Table 1 output voltage of 6 TEG

Time , s	Temperature difference, ΔT	TEG, V	MPPT 1, V	Super capacitor, V	MPPT 2, V
700	17.22	0.0576	0.5530	0.5576	5.01
1400	19.49	0.0578	0.5326	0.5322	5.037
2100	23.11	0.0629	0.5123	0.5118	5.035
2800	25.45	0.0782	0.5042	0.5042	5.037

B. Hybrid System Thermoelectric-Solar Performance

The hybrid system is the combination of TEG and PV to form a system. The setup of the experiment as shown figure below in the laboratory.

Figure 9 setup of hybrid system Thermoelectric-Solar

Table 2 output voltage from hybrid system

Masa, s	Permukaan panas, °C	Permukaan sejuk, °C	Hybrid, V	MPPT 1, V	Kapasitor Super, V	MPPT 2, V
700	52.73	28.92	0.068	0.1634	0.1621	1.288
1400	54.13	33.24	0.3962	0.1253	0.1087	1.285
2100	64.48	36.81	0.4089	0.2092	0.1901	1.288
2800	70.73	47.62	0.4033	0.1253	0.1011	1.277
3500	86.27	55.60	0.4775	0.6482	0.6021	4.975
4200	91.22	58.72	0.4877	0.8221	0.7979	4.973

For this experiment, hot plate not even used anymore. The only source is halogen lamp and TEG are put under PV panel. The heat dissipated from PV transferred to the TEG as the heat source. From table 2, second MPPT of hybrid system take 3500s to step up and for capacitor super continuous charging. Figure 10 below shows the result get from MATLAB software before connecting to MPPT and capacitor super and figure 11 when the system hybrid connected to MPPT. The hybrid system get the voltage 2.2V that is total from TEG and PV panel.

Figure 10 Output voltage of hybrid system

From the figure 11, the voltage from hybrid system are slightly decrease. This disturbance maybe cause by the external circuit resistance and the storing in capacitor super.

Figure 11 output voltage for the hybrid system connected to MPPT

C. testing hybrid system with the load (smartphone)

For this experiment two capacitor super were used, 5 μ F and 10 μ F with 2.5 V respectively. Figure 12 below shows that the hybrid system is capacitor super is charging until full. Based on the result, the storing voltage on the capacitor is only 4 V.

Figure 12 The charging of super-capacitor

Figure 13 The super-capacitor discharging to the load

Then, the system is connected to the load or for this experiment is smartphone. Figure 13 show the performance of capacitor super when the load is connected. When the load is connected to the capacitor super and power source is switch off simultaneously. Based on the graph, the capacitor super start to discharge the load, but its only last for 15-20 second. Then the source is connected again to the capacitor.

CONCLUSION

The hybrid thermoelectric-solar can increase the generate of voltage compare to stand alone PV and TEG system that is about 20-22%. The MPPT with step up converter can boost voltage up to 5 V with minimum input voltage 0.2V. Performance of capacitor super in charging smatphone is very low because the storing voltage is only 4V and cannot support the USB voltage (5V), so for future work maybe can use a large storage capacitor super with higher step up convertor or maybe can use voltage regulator to stabilize the voltage output.

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